

Türkiye

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Türkiye, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system but complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2013-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice¹, the Turkish higher education system comprises four types of HEIs:

- Public universities (including high technology institutes)
- Foundation universities
- Foundation vocational higher schools
- Other HEIs (universities and vocational higher schools established by Ministry of National Defence, Ministry of Interior and security organization)

The Turkish higher education system includes public and foundation institutions. While the finance of public universities is mainly provided by public resources, foundation universities basically charge tuition fees. Foundation universities are subjected to the same legal legislation as Public universities except for some administrative and financial issues. While Public and Foundation universities (including high technology institutes) are the two major types of HEIs in Türkiye, some vocational higher education institutions are also established by the Ministry of National Defence, the Ministry of Interior and the Security Organization.

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 below provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics by HEI type. Over 60% of all HEIs are Public universities (*Devlet universiteleri*), which are mostly public institutions and have the right to award PhDs. Also the 73 public Foundation universities (*Vakif universiteleri*) are all PhD awarding. Furthermore, there are Foundation vocational higher schools (*Vakif meslekyuksek okullari*) and Other higher education institutions (*Diğer yükseköğretim kurumları*). However, both types together only account for less than 3% of all HEIs. While the former are all private and non-PhD awarding, the latter ones are both public and one of them is PhD-awarding.

¹https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/eurydice/content/types-higher-education-institutions-101_en

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private	PhD awarding
Foundation university	Vakif Universiteleri	73	0	73	73
Foundation vocational higher school	Vakif Meslek Yuksek Okullari	4	0	4	0
Other HEI	Diğer yükseköğretim kurumları	2	2	0	1
Public university	Devlet Universiteleri	129	127	2	129
Total		208	129	79	203

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of Türkiye's higher education system and its evolution over time.

Figure 1 overleaf shows that despite ancient historical roots the expansion of the system in terms of the number of HEIs is relatively recent. In fact, the oldest Turkish university, the Istanbul University (Istanbul Üniversitesi), dates back to 1453. Only four other HEIs were founded before the 20th century. Until 1937, the year in which the first Other higher education institution was founded, only Public universities were present in Türkiye. The rise of Foundation universities, which are nowadays the second most numbered HEI type in Türkiye, began in 1984. The newest type of HEIs are Foundation vocational higher schools which have started to be established in 2008.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

Students

Figure 2 shows the percentage of enrolled student disaggregated by ISCED level for the different HEI types. With over 90% of the total students enrolled in Public universities, they are the leading actor in the Turkish higher education system followed by Foundation universities which enroll almost 8% of total students. With only 11,561 students attending Foundation vocational higher schools, they play a minor and negligible role in terms of enrolled students. This is because it has only been present in Türkiye since 2008 as shown in Figure 1. We also observe differences between educational levels: Public universities account for around 92% of the Bachelor and PhD students but only for around 84% of the Master long degree (without an intermediate bachelor's degree) students, and 83% of the Master students. Thus, Foundation universities seem to play a slightly more important role for receiving a master's degree compared to receiving a bachelor's or PhD degree.

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Total students include ISCED 5-7; Other Higher Education Institutions missing

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER provides a rich set of data moving beyond the information available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyse the composition of personnel by type of HEI and characteristics such as gender, nationality, educational field and, from 2020 onwards, levels of seniority.

As shown by Figure 3, there are major differences between HEIs in size, as measured by total personnel in head counts (HC) and in the personnel composition. With an average of nearly 1,178 HC, the Public Universities are the largest HEIs in the, followed by Foundation universities (average 377 HC). These differences reflect distinct levels of engagement in research and in education. As of the personnel composition, around 85% are academic personnel in Foundation University and 15% are research and teaching assistants. In Public universities the share of total academic personnel is a little smaller and accounts for around 76%. The rest are research and teaching assistants.

Figure 3. Personnel (HC) by category and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Data on support and administrative personnel is missing.

Since the data collection 2020, ETER also includes information on academic staff seniority level based on a classification jointly developed by OECD and EUROSTAT². Combined with information on gender, this information allows measuring two critical issues, i.e. career prospects of academic staff and the so-called leaky pipeline, i.e. the fact that the share of female academic staff decreases systematically with seniority levels.

As of Türkiye, data are available for Foundation universities, Public universities and Foundation vocational higher schools. Overall, there is some sign of the leaky pipeline although it is not as steep a hierarchy as in other countries. While 32% are female at the senior level, the share increases to 40% at the intermediate level. At the junior level, there is almost perfect gender balance with a share of 49% female personnel. Interestingly, the share of female junior personnel at the Foundation university (around 58%) and at the Foundation vocational higher schools (around 66%) is even larger than the male share.

² OECD (2022), Education at a Glance, Paris, pp. 412-413.

Figure 4. Academic personnel by seniority level and gender (HC), 2020

Note: Other HEIs are not included and reflected in the figure.

A final important dimension is internationality since it is generally considered as beneficial for the quality of research and education. In ETER, this is measured by the share of academic personnel not having the citizenship of the country ('foreigners'). As shown by Figure 5, the absolute share of foreign personnel is relatively small in both HEI types being largest in 2013 in Foundation universities with a share of around 7%. Comparing the change between the years 2013 and 2020, we see some differences between the two HEI types. While the share decreased by around 1.6 percentage points in Foundation universities, it stayed almost unchanged in Public universities rising by only around 0.4 percentage points.

Figure 5. Share of foreign academic personnel (HC) by type of HEI, 2013 and 2020

Changing roles over time

When observed through the lens of the number of students, data show a pattern of increase in the number of enrolled students increasing by almost 50% from 2013 to 2020. This growth was the largest for Foundation universities (about 79%) followed by Public universities (around 49%). The number of students in Foundation vocational higher schools even decreased by around 1% in the observed period of time. While the amount of attending students rose every year in Public and Foundation universities, it had its peak in 2016 in Foundation vocational higher schools decaying from 22,264 to 8,716 students in 2020. This decrease was partly caused by the transformation of these Foundation vocational higher schools into Universities.

Figure 6. Students enrolled by type of HEI, 2013-2020

As shown by **Error! Reference source not found.7**, with an increase of 24% from 2013 to 2020, the growth was not as the increase in the number of students between 2013 and 2020, Like for students, the increase of academic personnel was strongest in federal universities of technology followed by Public universities.

Figure 7. Academic personnel (FTE) by type of HEI, 2013-2020

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